

Fig. S1



Fig. S1. Morphometric PCA plot of 10 informative flowering traits of 212 plants in paired analysis of *C. howellii* (CAHO, purple triangles) and putative *C. howellii* (CAHOput, downward lavender triangles) versus *C. leichtlinii* ssp. *suksdorfii* (CALE, green diamonds). Traits in Appendix 2; species and site codes in Table 1, Fig. 2 map.